

Supplementary Materials for

Bio-inspired Synergistic Wing and Tail Morphing Extends Drone Flight Capabilities

E. Ajanic*, M. Feroskhan, S. Mintchev, F.Noca, D. Floreano*

*Corresponding authors: {enrico.ajanic,dario.floreano}@epfl.ch

This PDF file includes:

Supplementary Text

Fig. S1. Wing airfoils.

Fig. S2. Coordinate systems and variables.

Fig. S3. Wing and tail contribution to pitch stability.

Fig. S4. Standard deviation of lift and drag coefficient plots.

Fig. S5. Standard deviation of pitch and roll coefficient plots.

Mov. S1. Morphing wing fabrication.

Mov. S2. Morphing tail fabrication.

Mov. S3. Morphing control surfaces.

Mov. S4. Pull up maneuver.

Mov. S5. Flight test.

Supplementary References^{5,8,10,44}.

Supplementary Text

1 **Derivation of linear acceleration in the wind axis.** The linear accelerations
 2 acting on the aircraft's center of gravity in the wind frame wf (see Fig. S2) with the
 3 basis vectors \vec{e}_x , \vec{e}_y , and \vec{e}_z can be defined as

$$\vec{a}_{wf} = \underbrace{\dot{V}}_{=a_{wf,x}} \vec{e}_x + \underbrace{\dot{\psi}V \cos \gamma}_{=a_{wf,y}} \vec{e}_y + \underbrace{\dot{\gamma}V}_{=a_{wf,z}} \vec{e}_z \quad (\text{S1})$$

4 with \dot{V} being the change in path velocity of the aircraft, $\dot{\psi}$ being the change in path
 5 azimuth angle in the lateral plane, and $\dot{\gamma}$ being the change in heading angle in the
 6 longitudinal plane⁸.

7 Correspondingly, as commonly done in flight dynamics when analyzing the flight path
 8 behavior, the point-mass model is considered⁵. The relation between the resultant
 9 force vector \vec{F} and the acting force vectors, such as thrust \vec{T} , lift $\vec{L} = f(C_L, V, S, \dots)$,
 10 drag $\vec{D} = f(C_D, V, S, \dots)$, and weight $\vec{W} = f(m, g, \dots)$ can be shown and separated
 11 into the wind-fixed components so that

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F} &= \vec{T} + \vec{L} + \vec{D} + \vec{W} \\ &= [T \cos \varepsilon - D - W \sin \gamma] \vec{e}_x + [(T \sin \varepsilon + L) \sin \phi] \vec{e}_y - [(T \sin \varepsilon + L) \cos \phi - W \cos \gamma] \vec{e}_z. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2})$$

12 Here, the angle of climb is denoted with γ , the bank angle with φ , and deviation angle
 13 of the thrust with respect to the flight path with ε . Zero sideslip angle is assumed.
 14 Combining Eq. S1 and Eq. S2 yields the so-called dynamic equation in the wind-fixed
 15 frame based on the point-mass model⁵), so that

$$\vec{a}_{wf} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{V} \\ \dot{\psi}V \cos \gamma \\ \dot{\gamma}V \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{T \cos \varepsilon - D}{m} - g \sin \gamma \\ -\frac{(T \sin \varepsilon + L) \sin \varphi}{m} \\ \frac{(T \sin \varepsilon + L) \cos \varphi}{m} - g \cos \gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{S3})$$

16 As treated in the introduction, a large thrust force can evidently increase maneuver-
 17 ability, which is seen in Eq. S3. The thrust force affects the acceleration in every wind
 18 axis direction, however, the interest of this paper is in the leverage of aerodynamic
 19 forces on maneuverability, and hence gliding flight (gl) is assumed with $T = 0$, which
 20 simplifies Eq. S3 so that

$$\vec{a}_{wf,gl} = \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{x}_{wf} \\ \ddot{y}_{wf} \\ \ddot{z}_{wf} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{V} \\ \dot{\psi}V \cos \gamma \\ \dot{\gamma}V \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-D}{m} - g \sin \gamma \\ -\frac{L \sin \varphi}{m} \\ \frac{L \cos \varphi}{m} - g \cos \gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{S4})$$

21 Here, because calm wind conditions are assumed so that $\alpha = \gamma$, Eq. S4 simplifies to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{x}_{wf} \\ \ddot{y}_{wf} \\ \ddot{z}_{wf} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-D}{m} - g \sin \alpha \\ -\frac{L \sin \varphi}{m} \\ \frac{L \cos \varphi}{m} - g \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{S5})$$

22 Hence, the external variable that affects the linear acceleration in flight path direction
 23 \ddot{x}_{wf} is the drag force D , while accelerations perpendicular to the flight path direction
 24 (\ddot{y}_{wf} and \ddot{z}_{wf}) are affected by the lift force L .

25 **Derivation of pure rotational acceleration around the body fixed axes.** The
 26 dynamic aircraft equations of motion¹⁰ define the rotational acceleration acting around
 27 the aircraft's body fixed (*bf*) axes x_{bf} , y_{bf} , and z_{bf} such that

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{p} &= \frac{P + I_{xz}\dot{r} - qr(I_{zz} - I_{yy}) + I_{xz}pq}{I_{xx}} \\ \dot{q} &= \frac{Q - rq(I_{xx} - I_{zz}) - I_{xz}(p^2 - r^2)}{I_{yy}} \\ \dot{r} &= \frac{R + I_{xz}\dot{p} - pq(I_{yy} - I_{xx}) - I_{xz}qr}{I_{zz}}\end{aligned}\quad (S6)$$

28 where \dot{p} is the roll acceleration, \dot{q} is the pitch acceleration, \dot{r} is the yaw acceleration, p
 29 is the roll velocity, q is the pitch velocity, r is the yaw velocity, P is the roll moment,
 30 Q is the pitch moment, R is the yaw moment (see Fig. S2), and the elements of the
 31 moment of inertia tensor, such that

$$I = \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx} & I_{xy} & I_{xz} \\ I_{yx} & I_{yy} & I_{yz} \\ I_{zx} & I_{zy} & I_{zz} \end{bmatrix}.\quad (S7)$$

32 To estimate the effect of the external moments and the moment of inertia tensor on
 33 the LisHawk's agility in the respective aircraft fixed axis, the pure rotational motion
 34 is developed by assuming the rotational velocities of the other axes are zero, as stated
 35 in⁸. Thus, Eq. S6 reduces to the variables which can directly be influenced by the
 36 morphing wing and tail (P , Q , R , and I), such that

$$\dot{\Omega}_{pure} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{P}{I_{xx}} \\ \frac{Q}{I_{yy}} \\ \frac{R}{I_{zz}} \end{pmatrix}.\quad (S8)$$

37 **The tail's effect on static pitch stability.** The gradient of the pitch moment
 38 curve (pitching stiffness) is influenced by the location of the lifting surfaces, and can
 39 simplified (fuselage neglected, for small angles of attack) as

$$C_{m,\alpha} = -\frac{l_w}{\bar{c}_w} C_{Lw,\alpha} - \frac{S_t l_t}{S_w \bar{c}_w} \eta_t C_{Lt,\alpha} (1 - \epsilon_{d,\alpha})\quad (S9)$$

40 where $C_{Lw,\alpha}$ is the lift slope of the main wing, $C_{Lt,\alpha}$ is the lift slope of the tail, l_w
 41 is the distance between the center of gravity and the center of lift, l_t is the distance
 42 between the tail's center of lift and the center of gravity, S_w is the main wing's area,
 43 S_t is the area of the tail, \bar{c}_w is the mean chord of the main wing, η_t is the efficiency of
 44 the tail dependent on the flow quality arriving the elevator, and $\epsilon_{d,\alpha}$ is the downwash
 45 angle of the flow arriving at the tail⁸. Fig. S3 depicts the relations of the variables
 46 above in a schematic. To simplify Eq. S9, we assume $\eta_h = 1$ and $\epsilon_{d,\alpha} = 0$ so that

$$C_{m,\alpha} = -\frac{l_w}{\bar{c}_w} C_{Lw,\alpha} - \frac{S_t l_t}{S_w \bar{c}_w} C_{Lt,\alpha}.\quad (S10)$$

47 The lift slopes, the wing planform areas, the distance l_t (aft tail configuration) and the
48 mean aerodynamic chord are always positive. The change in l_t is small and it is hence
49 assumed to be constant. From Eq. S10 it is accessible that the wing-tail combination
50 is unconditionally stable if the center of gravity is in front of the center of lift, meaning
51 that $l_w > 0$. For the LisHawk, shifting the wing into tucked wing increases l_w which
52 increases longitudinal stability. A similar effect can be expected when the LisHawks
53 tail area is increased. Contrarily, by sweeping the wing forward, l_w is reduced and
54 can even become negative, hence becoming negative stable (unstable).

Fig. S1: Airfoil selection of the LisHawk compared to the goshawk's wing. **a** Airfoils obtained from the XFLR5 simulations for the three distinguishable wing sections of the LisHawk wing. **b** Illustration of the undercambered airfoils of a northern goshawk wing⁴⁴ to compare with the LisHawk wing.

Fig. S2: Coordinate systems and variables used for describing the agility and maneuverability metrics used in this paper. The red/white filled circle is the center of gravity. **a** Side view: Variables describing the side view are the x -axis in the body fixed frame x_{bf} , the z -axis in the body fixed frame z_{bf} (perpendicular to x_{bf}), the wind frame x -axis x_{wf} , the wind frame z -axis z_{wf} (perpendicular to x_{wf}), the angle of attack α , the flight velocity V , the lift L , the drag D , the pitching moment Q , and the pitching acceleration \dot{q} . **b** Front view: Variables describing the front view are the y -axis in the body fixed frame y_{bf} (perpendicular to x_{bf} and z_{bf}), the y -axis in the wind fixed frame y_{wf} (perpendicular to x_{wf} and z_{wf}), the bank angle φ , the roll moment P , and the roll acceleration \dot{p} . **c** Top view: Variables describing the top view are yawing moment R and the yawing acceleration \dot{r} . The sideslip angle is assumed to be small and hence the wind fixed axes are equal to the body fixed axes

Fig. S3: Physical parameters that influence the pitch stability and their relation with the LisHawk platform. Two lifting surfaces influencing the pitching stiffness can be distinguished: (i) The pitching moment caused by the main wing at a certain angle of attack α is influenced by the lift force L_w and the drag force D_w (perpendicular to L_w and parallel to the path velocity acting on the wing V_w) and the lever arm l_w . (ii) The tail's contribution is a function of the tail's lever arm l_t , the tail's lift L_t and the tail's drag D_t . The drag force is again parallel to the incoming airflow V_t , which is different from α by ϵ_d due to the downwash generated by the main wing.

Fig. S4: Standard deviation the lift and drag plots depending on the wing and tail sweep and the vertical tail deflection with respect to the angle of attack. The shaded areas indicate the standard deviation. The solid line indicates an elevation of 0° , the dashed line an elevation of 20° (downward), and the dash-dotted line indicates an elevation of -20° (upward). **a** Lift and drag coefficient when the wing and tail are tucked. **b** Lift and drag coefficient when the wing is tucked and the tail extended. **c** Lift and drag coefficient when the wing is extended and the tail tucked. **d** Lift and drag coefficient when the wing and tail are extended.

Fig. S5: Standard deviation the pitch moment plots depending on the wing and tail sweep and the vertical tail deflection with respect to the angle of attack. The shaded areas indicate the standard deviation. The solid line indicates an elevation of 0° , the dashed line an elevation of 20° (downward), and the dash-dotted line indicates an elevation of -20° (upward). **a** Pitch coefficient when wing and tail are tuckered. **b** Pitch coefficient when the wing is tuckered and the tail extended. **c** Pitch coefficient when the wing is extended and the tail tuckered. **d** Pitch coefficient when the wing and tail are extended. **e** Roll coefficient for two different wing asymmetries.

56 **Supplementary Movies**

57 **Mov. S1. Morphing wing fabrication.** This movie shows each assembly step of
58 the wing morphing mechanism and provides information on the materials used.

59 **Mov. S2. Morphing tail fabrication.** This movie shows the assembly steps of
60 the tail mechanism and the materials used.

61 **Mov. S3. Control degrees-of-freedom.** This movie shows the LisHawk's morph-
62 ing capabilities.

63 **Mov. S4. Pull-up maneuver.** Pull-up maneuver for all three cases of tucked wing
64 and tail, tucked wing and extended tail, and extended wing and tail to show increased
65 agility and maneuverability due to morphing.

66 **Mov. S5. Flight test.** This video shows the LisHawk in flight in different morphing
67 configurations and flight regimes and its behavior during aggressive and cruising flight.